

SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS OF DAIRY PRODUCTS AND THEIR PHYSIOLOGICAL EFFECTS ON THE HUMAN ORGANISM

Yaqubjanova Yoqutkhan Gulomjanovna¹

¹Namangan Civil Engineering Institute, senior teacher at the Labor Protection and Ecology Department

Sariboyeva Diloram Akramjonovna²

²Senior lecturer (PhD) of the Department of Food Technology, Namangan Institute of Engineering Technology

Halimjonova Umida Bakhtiyar's³

³daughter- is a student of Namangan Engineering and Construction Institute
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ANNOTATION

This article is now aimed at the effective use of secondary raw materials that are formed during the processing of milk and dairy products in our republic, as well as the introduction of waste-free technologies that allow you to obtain products whose composition is rich in useful nutrients.

Keywords: milk fat, proteins, mineral salts, dry matter, lactose, dairy products, dairy secondary raw materials, casein, biologically active substances, preventive, therapeutic, functional drink.

INTRODUCTION

Milk and milk products are popular among Uzbek consumers. The dairy products market is extremely competitive, and the manufacture of targeted final goods is inefficient. The majority of milk (up to 50%) is utilized in the production system to make cheese, cottage cheese, and casein, while the remainder is used to make secondary raw materials (whey). Given the great biological value of whey as well as the large volume of production, it is impossible to get a high result (profit) without employing it correctly. The amount and efficiency with which secondary milk resources are used assures the enterprise's profitability. The main aspect of resolving the problems of reducing the environmental burden of milk processing enterprises is the proper organization of the whey processing scheme.

Obtaining milk on an industrial scale is now connected with significant expenses, thus it is critical to utilize all of the components of milk fully and logically.

Secondary raw materials - sardine and whey - are created during the processing of milk into butter, cheese, curds, and 1 ton of butter creates 1.5 tons of adobe (cotton), and 1 ton of cheese and curd produces up to 9 tons of whey. However, such a healing boon is not regenerated and is nearly immediately discarded.

It is well known that the composition of milk's secondary raw materials is high in protein, milk fat, carbs, and mineral salts. All of the vital components of milk, such as vitamins, enzymes, hormones, and organic acids, are transferred to secondary raw materials of milk. Whey's choline content boosts brain capacity and memory. One liter of whey meets an adult's daily calcium need and 40% of their potassium requirement. Whey is also high in uncommon mineral salts like phosphorus and magnesium.

This liquid comprises 200 different types of physiologically active chemicals that have a good influence on the activity of all organs in the body. Whey consumption benefits the digestive tract by cleaning it, normalizing its flora, expelling toxins, and improving liver and kidney function. It is beneficial to the adrenal glands. The valuable amino acids in yogurt whey are extremely important to the body and actively engage in protein metabolism and blood production. Serum is quite beneficial in the treatment of gastrointestinal problems, stomach ulcers, constipation, pancreatitis, enterocolitis, dysbacteriosis, abdominal rest illnesses, atherosclerosis prevention, blood pressure, ischemic heart failure, and cerebral circulation disorders.

By beginning the manufacturing of nutrient-rich soft drinks from these milk secondary raw materials, it is feasible to develop waste-free technologies and extend the variety of goods.

The chemical composition, energy or nutritional value, and physical qualities of secondary milk raw materials are heavily influenced by the manufacturing process. Almost all chemicals found in milk are now transmitted to some extent to secondary milk source materials.

Table 1 shows the estimated concentration (in %) of the key components in milk, skimmed milk, cotton, and whey compared to milk.

Table 1

Components	Milk	Lactose-free milk	Cotton	Whey
Mass fraction of dry matter	12,5	8,9	9,1	6,3
Milk fat	3,7	0,05	0,5	0,2
Protein	3,3	3,3	3,3	0,8
Lactose	4,8	4,8	4,7	4,8
Mineral substances	0,7	0,75	0,7	0,5

Table 2 shows the rate of transformation of the major components of milk to secondary milk raw materials.

Table 2

Milk components	Passing rate, in %		
	Lactose-free milk	Cotton	Whey
Milk fat	1,4	14	5,5
Protein, including casein	99,6	99,4	24,3
	99,5	99,5	22,5
Lactose	99,5	99,4	96
Mineral salts	99,8	99,6	98
Dry matter	70,4	72,8	52

Whey is a byproduct of cheese, cottage cheese, and casein manufacture. The quantitative content of whey changes according to the type of cheese made the quantity of fat in it, and the manner of production.

Casein and milk fat are the primary components employed in the manufacture of fatty cheeses, with the remainder being transferred to whey in substantial quantities. Casein should be utilized as much as feasible, fat as needed for the type of cheese being made, and milk sugar and mineral salts as needed for the cheese to mature. The recommended quantity of milk sugar in the manufacturing of hard cheeses is 10% (5-7% on average), however this varies according to the kind of cheese. Milk normally contains 3-5% mineral salts. During the cheese curd formation process, calcium and phosphorus salts are transported to the cheese.

Table 3

Whey Composition and Properties

Indicators	Whey		
	Cheese whey	Cottage cheese whey	Casein whey
Amount of dry matter, %, milk fat protein lactose mineral salts	4,5-7,2	4,2-7,4	4,5-7,5
	0,05-0,5	0,05-0,4	0,02-0,1
	0,5-1,1	0,5 - 1,4	0,5 - 1,5
	3,9 - 4,9	3,2 - 5,1	3,5 - 5,2
	0,3 - 0,8	0,5 - 0,8	0,3 - 0,9
Acidity, °T	15 - 25	50 - 85	50 - 120

pH	6,3	4,4	4,3
Density, kg/m ³	1018 – 1027	1019 – 1026	1020 – 1025

CONCLUSION

According to the information provided, whey is one of the most beneficial blessings, and its value to the human body is equal to that of cottage cheese, cheese, and sour cream. Whey is high in vitamins A, E, C, and B vitamins, and the extremely uncommon vitamins V4 and V7. Whey contains chlorine, which boosts brain capacity and memory. One liter of whey meets an adult's daily calcium need and 40% of their potassium requirement. Whey also contains uncommon mineral salts like phosphorus and magnesium.

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